

Quantum Mechanics From Inertia Transforming Into Independent E and p Values?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 4, 2026

In previous notes, we argued that one could describe elastic two particle collisions, even in Newtonian mechanics, in a classical statistical manner. In particular, we argued that one could introduce a probability which depends on E,p, but at the same time has the same weight (in a sense) for any free particle. Product probabilities would be linked with a uniform distribution in the sense that $\exp(-iE_1)\exp(-iE_2) = \exp(-iE_3)\exp(-iE_4)$ if $E_1+E_2=E_3+E_4$ and a similar expression for momentum. If one respects the special relativistic invariant $-Et+px$, then a possible solution is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but even though this yields the free particle wavefunction (probability), this does not explain quantum mechanics. These are simply ideas of classical probability theory with the enforced special relativistic invariant $-Et+px$.

Here, we argue that the real feature leading to quantum mechanics (the idea of \hbar/p and \hbar/E) arises from the notion of inertia (which we have argued in previous notes also gives rise to spin). We argue that a single force (inertia) in a rest frame becomes two independent interaction notions, E and p as well as creating x' as a running variable. Thus, m, t and E, t' and p, x' are intertwined. We suggest that there must be a physical mechanism which keeps these two concepts E,p independent and so one cannot simply rely on $x=vt$. Given the Lorentz invariant and the classical notion of probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, one must go one step further and postulate that there are independent fluctuations in t' and x' in such a calculation such that \hbar/E and \hbar/p emerge. We argue that this is a key feature of quantum mechanics and that it does not immediately arise from $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ if one only considers $x=vt$. One is forced to allow x, t to fluctuate independently which leads to a fluctuation in m in the rest frame as well. We argue that this feature is actually associated with special relativity as it allows a single force inertia to manifest itself as two independent interaction quantities E,p.

As a result, we suggest that one may obtain $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ without any notion of probability, but only by postulating the existence of a physical mechanism (fluctuation of x', t' or t in the rest frame) which keeps E,p independent because $-Et+px$ does not ensure their independence if one only considers $x=vt$. One may then interpret $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as having the form of a classical probability which respects special relativity.

Classical Probability Theory

We argue that classical probability theory does not directly lead to quantum features. In particular, quantum features such as wavelength, frequency and spin are physical and one must account for this physical behaviour.

In previous notes, we have argued that even in Newtonian mechanics, one may introduce classical probability to account for elastic collisions (which conserve both E energy and p momentum). We have argued that each free particle must have the same weight (because there is no distribution of energy), but the probability must also depend on E and p. Using the notion of a uniform distribution, one might suggest:

$$\exp(iE C_1) \exp(i p C_2) \quad C_1, C_2 \text{ constants for units, } p \text{ in one dimension} \quad ((1))$$

If one tries to make ((1)) special relativistically invariant, then one might propose:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Mathematically, this leads to the notion of:

$$\Delta x = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t = \hbar/E \quad ((3))$$

The problem is that there is no physical reason for ((3)) from classical probability theory. Simply introducing the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ also does not lead to ((3)) if one insists on:

$$x=vt \quad ((4))$$

The only way to achieve ((3)) is to allow for independent fluctuations in x, t in ((2)). We argue, however, that there must be physical motivation for this and the objective of this note is to investigate this.

The Notion of Inertia

Mathematically, $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant, and it is this function which introduces x, t into ((2)). $x=vt$, however, directly links x to t in special relativity. We suggest that one must focus on the notion of m_0 , inertia, which is a single force. At the same time $m_0 c^2$ is energy. As seen from a moving frame ($-v$ constant), one has E and p and these are dependent in the sense that:

$$p/E = v \quad \text{for} \quad c=1 \quad ((5))$$

but, are independent in terms of physical interactions. P (momentum) is linked with a direct impulse hit, while E is more often associated with changes over an x range. We argue that there must be some physical mechanism which enforces this independence as $-Et+px$, the Lorentz invariant cannot do so with $x=vt$.

We start with m_0 , a force (inertia) and at the same time an energy, at rest. This means that $x=0$ (if one wishes), but that t is a running variable. From the moving frame, x' and t' become running variables. It is as if x' and p are being created as new variables, with E and p representing separate interaction features. For example, E may be constant while a particle reflects and $p \rightarrow -p$. If one only considers $x=vt$ ((4)), which holds for special relativity, then the independence of E and p does not seem to emerge.

One might argue that there is no reason to introduce the classical probability ((1)). In particular, one might argue that this is an approximate approach, which is fine, but that ultimately one does not need to introduce the notion of classical probability. If that is the case, then one does not have ((2)) a priori. Nevertheless, we have argued that for any free particle, there must be a physical mechanism which ensures that E, p remain independent concepts as $-Et+px$ does not enforce this with $x=vt$. Given that E, p are independent and postulating a physical mechanism which enforces this, it seems to follow that this mechanism must exist

already in the rest frame with m_0 . In such a case, the mechanism simply separates out E and p as independent entities. The question then becomes: What possible mechanism can be associated with a rest mass (inertia) m_0 ? It is simply a mass at rest linked with a running t . The interesting idea, however, seems to be that it is not simply $m_0 c^2$ which becomes E, p , but $x=0, t$ which becomes x', t' . In other words, E, p and x', t' and m_0, t are closely linked and not simply independent notions, we argue.

If one takes this idea seriously, one may consider the Lorentz invariant:

$$-m_0 c^2 t \rightarrow -E' t' + p x' \quad ((6))$$

It is understood that $x' = vt'$, but we suggest that there is an additional physical mechanism linked with $m_0 c^2$ and t being associated and $-E' t' + p x'$. This mechanism must keep E and p independent in a physical sense and also in a special relativistic sense. The special relativistic function of interest is $-E' t' + p x' = -m_0 c^2 t$. This, however, does not represent any mechanism which keeps E and p independent. Given that t is a running variable for m_0 , it seems that t might be the variable which keeps m_0 independent and x' and t' , the variables which keep p (one dimension) and E independent. At this point, there is no notion of probability whatsoever, only independence of E and p . If x' and t' are to keep p, E independent, then one cannot have $x = vt$. This suggests that in addition to $x = vt$ describing the center-of-mass, there must be a fluctuation mechanism in x' and t' which keeps E and p independent. In other words, one seeks a function:

$$F(-E t + p x) = F_1(-E t) F_2(p x) \text{ for independence } ((7))$$

One may note that one may have E constant and p changing and so $F_1(-E t)$ could factor out in such a case. Given the relation $-E t + p x$, one expects $F_1 = F_2$. This suggests a power law, so one may write:

$$\exp(-E t + p x) \quad ((8))$$

The problem is that ((8)) grows uncontrollably and there is no sense of fluctuation. To obtain such a more reasonable function, one may consider:

$$\exp(-i E t + i p x) \quad ((9))$$

At this point, there is no sense of probability, but one cannot help but notice that

$$\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i (p_1 + p_2) x) \text{ and a similar expression for } E \quad ((10))$$

This suggests that ((9)) is linked to a classical probability, even though it was derived without any notion of probability. As a result, the independence of E, p from special relativity seems to lead to an inherent physical mechanism of fluctuating x', t' values which is of the form of a classical probability function.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried, in previous notes, to derive the free particle probability (wavefunction) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ from notions of classical probability. In particular, we sought a function of E, p that had the same weight for all free particles and respected a uniform distribution for E and p in the case of elastic two-body collisions. If one further wishes to respect special relativity, one may postulate $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, using the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. The problem with this probability is that if one enforces $x=vt$, one does not have $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. To obtain these, one requires independent fluctuations of x and t and it seems that a priori, there is no justification for this. We thus suggest that one needs to examine special relativity closely to try to justify a physical mechanism which creates an inherent probability for a particle..

We consider a rest mass m_0 , which represents force (inertia), but at the same time energy $m_0 c^2$ and is directly linked with a running time t as one may set $x=0$. A frame moving with $-v$ (constant) creates the sense of p (an independent interaction variable) as well as creating x' as a running variable, together with E, t' . Thus, m_0, t transforms into two independent interaction pieces $-Et'$ and px' which are linked with very different physical interactions, e.g. interaction over x versus a sharp impulse hit. We suggest that a physical mechanism must exist to allow for $-Et+px$ to physically enforce this independence of E, p as $-Et+px$ with $x=vt$ does not accomplish this. Furthermore, this mechanism must exist in the rest frame with m_0 . This then seems to be additional physics, beyond $x=vt$ and Newtonian mechanics. It is a mechanism associated with the inherent force m_0 (inertia). (We have also argued in previous notes that m_0 is directly linked with spin as well.) As a result, quantum mechanics ($\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and spin) seem to be directly tied to an inherent force and special relativity. We suggest that $-Et+px$ should be the argument of a separable function for the independent $-Et$ and px . This suggests a power law or $\exp(-Et+px)$. This, however, grows and so we propose $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ without using any notion of probability. It is at this point that one may notice that this function is linked with a uniform product probability distribution for two body elastic collisions as well as giving each free particle the same weight (i.e. a unit modulus of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$). As a result, we suggest that independence of E, p linked to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ leads to the notion of an inherent physical manifestation which requires fluctuating x', t' , i.e. probability together with the deterministic $x=vt$ associated with the center-of-mass.